

USE OF POWER POINT SOFTWARE IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING CLASSROOMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7807553>

Annotation: This article highlights power point software's features, it's usage in English language. Additionally, it covers about both benefits and negatives using it in teaching english to students. In this article, benefits of using power point are organized lessons , time management , and creative an interesting atmosphere to students. However, the drawbacks of using power point can be seen by not being able to add extra ideas and information during a teacher 's speech. Furthermore , it involves inappropriate use of multimedia options and poor quality of slides as well as being a lot of text on a slide. By this way, teachers have to follow the outline which is done by a teacher in advance, even though they want to give more information during a lesson.

Key words: Power point software, Information Communication Technology, Microsoft Office, presentation, tool, multimedia.

Today's world is highly dominated by technology. It has created several changes in all aspects of the society for its betterment and progress. Information Communication Technology (ICT) has been increasingly growing day by day along with globalization. ICT is playing a significant role in its global profusion in the field of education along with integration of technology. With widespread use of ICT in the field of education , immense increment has been observed in the use of Power Point software which is included in the " Microsoft Office" package programs as a supporting teaching tool that is powerful presentation material in all modern classrooms.

Power Point is a software program which is using in today's world to improve the quality of teaching English language and other foreign languages. Additionally, it covers another field except from education. Creating presentations ; adding text, images , and videos ; choosing a professional design ; adding transition, animations , and cinematic motion can be good examples of the features of Power Point software. Using Power Point software is a demand of today's modern world to ease and make much quicker the process of teaching English to students. It is believed that Power Point presentation give a way to develop both teachers and students.

There are both benefits and negatives of using Power Point presentations in classrooms.

Benefits of using Power Point presentations:

- learners can be exposed to various forms of visual information
- help display effective and appropriate written material
- lecturers can also deliver slides before the class , which can help learners comprehend the lecture notes on their own which leads to self- study
- being extra time to revise the lesson as the lesson outline is made up before and does not take much time.

Drawbacks of using Power Point presentations:

- irritating noise and slide transition
- tendency to go too fast is common simply because of the ease of delivery of the material
- inappropriate use of multimedia options
- too much text put on a slide detracting from its legibility.

To attract students attention Power Point presentations are very useful indeed. It can create an interesting atmosphere to learn English for students. However, it has some drawbacks which is mentioned above. Most of negatives are depended on computer literacy . Computer literacy is an ability can use all the features of Power Point software. If not, the slides will be boring and poor quality to show everyone. Additionally, there are a lot of text which is put on a slide , it can be great difficulty some students who have seeing problems, even it can be invisible to health students. Furthermore, teachers can go fast while explaining new terms or theme. As a result, students can not be able to gain knowledge fully which is provided by teachers and it leads to misunderstanding of a new theme.

As for advantages of using Power Point software, it can motivate students to learn more about a theme and revise it after explaining by a teacher. Because, by using Power Point presentations, teachers can use their time effectively and they have an extra time to revise the new theme. Importantly, students have an access to gain knowledge visually . Visual learning is really helpful to students as it provides to get more than 50% of the given knowledge. As a result, students begin developing their knowledge.

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